

Scheme 1

ing a free radical intermediate². No free radical has been detected in this reaction. This observation and also the absence of products like naphthyl alcohol and dinaphthyl, which would have been formed if a free radical mechanism were operative, validate this ionic mechanism involving the direct conversation of α -methylnaphthalene to α -naphthaldehyde.

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References

1. C. F. CULLIS and J. W. LADBURY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 555.
2. K. B. WIBERG, "Oxidation in Organic Chemistry", Academic Press, New York, 1965, p. 1.
3. W. A. WATERS, *Quart Rev.*, 1958, 12, 281.
4. W. A. WATERS, *Quart Rev.*, 1958, 12, 296

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Cycloalkanols by *N*-Chlorosaccharin

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THE kinetics of oxidation of alcohols by *N*-halo compounds¹⁻³ have been studied by different workers. In our earlier paper⁴ we reported the title reaction by *N*-bromosaccharin. In this paper, we present the kinetics of oxidation of cyclic alcohols by *N*-chlorosaccharin (NCSacc) in aqueous acetic acid medium with a view to find out the

nature of reactive species, ring reactivity and to propose a suitable mechanism.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade and purified further by distillation. Acetic acid (AnalaR) was refluxed over chromium trioxide. The middle fraction boiling at 117–118° (lit. 118.5°) was used. Cyclopentanol, cyclohexanol, cycloheptanol and cyclooctanol were Fluka AG samples. Oxidant was prepared by chlorination of saccharin by the usual procedure⁵. The purity of the compound is checked by tlc.

The reactions were carried out in 40% (v/v) acetic acid–water mixture at 30–50° at the desired sulphuric acid concentration (0.025–0.4 *M*). The kinetics of the reaction were followed by estimating the unreacted oxidant iodometrically⁴. All the experiments were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions using ten-fold excess of [substrate] over the [oxidant]. The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined by keeping the excess of oxidant concentration over substrate and estimating the unreacted oxidant concentration from time to time.

Results and Discussion

The stoichiometry of the reaction was found to be one mole of alcohol to one mole of oxidant as given by the equation.

The products obtained were the corresponding ketones which were identified by preparing the corresponding 2,4-DNP derivatives and comparing their melting points with the literature⁶ value. Chloride ions were identified by the usual test. When acrylonitrile was added to the reaction mixture, no polymerisation was observed indicating that the reaction did not involve free radicals as well as confirms the absence of one-electron transformation. The rate of reaction was not affected by added saccharin indicating that there was no formation of saccharin in pre-equilibrium step. This was contrary to our earlier observations on alcohol oxidation by *N*-bromosaccharin⁴. At the same time, the rate was not affected by added salts like Na_2SO_4 . The order with respect to oxidant was found to be unity from the linear plots of $\log(a-x)$ vs time. However, the observed first order rate constants are slightly decreasing by increasing the oxidant concentration (Table 1). This is indicative of a prior equilibrium involving *N*-chlorosaccharin and other nucleophilic species present⁷ (probably H_2O). The observed rate constants are increasing linearly by increasing the substrate concentration in

the range of 0.01–0.08 M (Table 2). A plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $\log [\text{substrate}]$ is a straight line for all the cyclolcohols studied with a slope equal to unity indicating first order dependence on substrate. The plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{substrate}]$ is linear passing through origin, which indicates the absence of formation of stable complex. In order to find out the influence of sulphuric acid on rate of reaction, experiments were carried out in the acid concentration range 0.025–0.4 M (Table 3). A plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $\log [H^+]$ is a straight line with a slope equal to less than unity, indicating a fractional order dependence on $[H^+]$.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF [NCSacc] ON k_{obs} IN CYCLIC ALCOHOL–NCSacc SYSTEM

[Substrate]=0.02 M, $[H_2SO_4]=0.1$ M, Temp.=318 K, HOAc–H₂O=40 : (v/v)

[Substrate]	$k_{\text{obs}} \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$ at [NCSacc]/M				
	0.001	0.002	0.003	0.004	0.005
Cyclopentanol	1.83	1.67	1.42	1.35	1.4
Cyclohexanol	14.08	11.96	10.75	9.10	8.85
Cycloheptanol	3.42	2.95	2.01	1.85	1.52
Cyclooctanol	4.02	3.41	3.21	2.95	2.65

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF [SUBSTRATE] ON k_{obs} IN CYCLIC ALCOHOL–NCSacc SYSTEM

[NCSacc]=0.002 M, $[H_2SO_4]=0.05$ M, HOAc–H₂O=60 : 40 (v/v), Temp.=318 K

[Substrate] M	$k_{\text{obs}} \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$			
	Cyclo-pentanol*	Cyclo-hexanol	Cyclo-heptanol	Cyclo-octanol
0.01	2.51	3.20	5.30	6.92
0.02	4.27	7.00	10.60	13.50
0.03	7.99	11.22	17.85	20.41
0.04	10.97	17.44	21.94	26.80
0.05	14.13	21.38	28.79	31.62
0.06	17.45	31.99	34.67	—
0.08	23.44	34.67	—	—
From plot of log-log Slope	1.10	1.20	1.05	0.95
Correlation coefficient	0.996	0.996	0.999	0.999

* $[H_2SO_4]=0.2$ M

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF $[H_2SO_4]$ ON k_{obs} IN CYCLIC ALCOHOL–NCSacc SYSTEM

[NCSacc]=0.002 M, [Substrate]=0.02 M, HOAc–H₂O=40 : 60 (v/v), Temp.=318 K

$[H_2SO_4]$ M	$k_{\text{obs}} \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$ at $[H_2SO_4]$		
	Cyclo-pentanol	Cyclo-hexanol	Cyclo-heptanol
0.025	0.66	3.67	1.15
0.05	0.96	6.76	1.86
0.1	1.63	11.96	2.95
0.2	3.23	21.37	4.67
0.3	4.04	27.41	5.88
0.4	5.29	—	7.07
Correlation coefficient	0.996	0.999	0.999

The effect of dielectric constant on the rate of reaction was studied in the range 20–90% (v/v)

acetic acid–water mixture (Table 4). The rate increases with decreasing dielectric constant of the medium. A plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/D$ is a straight line with a positive slope, indicating that the reaction is between an ion and dipole.

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF SOLVENT COMPOSITION ON k_{obs} IN CYCLIC ALCOHOL–NCSacc SYSTEM

[NCSacc]=0.002 M, [Substrate]=0.02 M, $[H_2SO_4]=0.05$ M, Temp.=318 K

Acetic acid %	$k_{\text{obs}} \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$ at different % HOAc in H ₂ O (v/v)		
	Cyclo-pentanol*	Cyclo-hexanol	Cyclo-heptanol
20	2.79	5.91	0.94
30	2.74	—	1.10
40	3.23	6.76	1.86
50	3.34	6.98	3.09
60	4.27	7.00	10.60
70	5.90	8.84	12.79
80	8.33	12.79	17.06
90	21.37	23.99	—

* $[H_2SO_4]=0.2$ M

In order to calculate the thermodynamic parameters, the reaction was studied at 30, 35, 40, 45 and 50°. The activation parameters have been calculated from Arrhenius plots and data are recorded in Table 5. The nearly same free energy of activation and linear Exner's⁸ plot ($\log k_{\text{obs}}^{50}$ vs $\log k_{\text{obs}}^{30}$) suggests that a similar type of mechanism is operative in all alcohols studied.

TABLE 5—ORDER OF REACTIVITY AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS IN CYCLIC ALCOHOL–NCSacc SYSTEM

[NCSacc]=0.002 M, HOAc–H₂O=40 : 60 (v/v), Temp.=318 K, $[H_2SO_4]=0.1$ M, [Substrate]=0.02 M

Substrate	$k_s \times 10^8$ l mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	ΔE^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹
Cyclopentanol	8.35	85.13	82.49	26	90.8
Cyclohexanol	59.31	76.62	73.98	36	85.5
Cycloheptanol	14.75	76.62	73.98	48	89.2
Cyclooctanol	17.06	76.62	73.98	47	88.8

N-Chlorosaccharin, like other similar N-halo compounds, may exist in various forms in acid medium⁹ as per the following equilibria,

According to our observations, there is no effect of saccharin on the rate of reaction indicating the absence of saccharin formation in a pre-equilibrium step. This shows that the reactive species of oxidant is not HOCl or H₂O⁺Cl. A plot of k_{obs} vs $[H^+]$ shows that there may be a reaction between alcohol–oxidant and alcohol–protonated species. This shows that the reactive species of oxidant might be free N-chlorosaccharin as well as protonated N-chlorosaccharin.

Taking all these facts into consideration, the protonated form of oxidant along with the free

N-chlorosaccharin are proposed as active forms of oxidant participating in the oxidation process. We suggest the following mechanism in which the alcohol attacks the active species of oxidant in the rate determining step,

Based on this mechanism the following rate expression can be obtained,

Rate = k_1 [substrate] [oxidant] + $K_2 k_3$ [substrate] [H⁺] [oxidant] and $k_{\text{obs}} = k_1$ [substrate] + $K_2 k_3$ [substrate] [H⁺], which explains first order in substrate and oxidant respectively and fractional order in H⁺. An attempt has been made to evaluate the rate constants k_1 , $K_2 k_3$ and $k_1 + K_2 k_3$ [H⁺] for cyclopentanol and cyclohexanol. The calculated values are given in Table 6.

TABLE 6—CALCULATED VALUES OF k_1 , K_2 , k_3 AND $k_1 + K_2 k_3$ [H⁺]

Substrate	$k_1 \times 10^3$ l mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	$K_2 k_3 \times 10^3$ l ² mol ⁻² s ⁻¹	$[k_1 + K_2 k_3$ [H ⁺]] $\times 10^3$
Cyclopentanol	1.9	3.12	1.44 at 0.4 M H ⁺
Cyclohexanol	5.0	25.0	1.50 at 0.04 M H ⁺

The kinetic evidence for the oxidation of cyclic alcohols by *N*-bromosaccharin and *N*-chlorosaccharin shows that different types of mechanism is operating in both the cases. This may be attributed due to the difference in electronegativities of the halo substituents¹⁰. Such type of observation was marked by Venkatasubramanian *et al.*^{1,2} during the oxidation of alcohols by *N*-chlorosuccinimide and *N*-bromosuccinimide.

The rate data given in Table 5 shows that under similar experimental conditions, the order of reactivity for all the alcohols studied above 40% (v/v) acetic acid–water is cyclohexanol > cyclooctanol > cycloheptanol > cyclopentanol. Similar order of reactivity is observed in the oxidation of cyclanols by VV.

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References

- V. THIAGARAJAN and N. VENKATASUBRAMANIAN, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1967, 3349, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, 8, 809.
- N. S. SRINIVASAN and N. VENKATASUBRAMANIAN, *Tetrahedron*, 1974, 30, 419.

- R. NATARAJAN and V. THIAGARAJAN, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1975, 1590.
- K. V. MOHAN, P. RAGHUNATHA RAO and E. V. SUNDARAM, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, 61, 876.
- F. D. CHITAWAY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 1884.
- A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 3rd ed., Longmans Green, London, 1961, p. 346.
- V. MANOHARAN and N. VENKATASUBRAMANIAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, 23, 889.
- O. EXNER, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1972, 37, 425.
- H. S. DAWN, I. H. PITMAN, T. HIGUCHI and S. YOUNG, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1970, 59, 955.
- S. M. FARROK, S. SIVAKAMASUNDARI and S. VISWANATHAM, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, 23, 289.
- R. NATARAJAN and N. VENKATASUBRAMANIAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1979, 17, 257.

Thermodynamics of Ionic Association in Aqueous Solutions of Sodium Salts of some Aromatic Carboxylic Acids using Ion-selective Electrode Technique

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THE newly developed ion-selective electrodes¹ have found very useful application in the study of the ion-association processes in solutions. A recent review² has been published concerning its use in this important area. In an earlier series of publications, we have applied this method to study the association in some important inorganic salts³⁻⁵ and organic salts⁶⁻⁹ in aqueous media.

In this paper, we report the application of the same technique to obtain thermodynamic data of the association process of sodium ion with *m*-hydroxybenzoate, 3,5-dihydroxybenzoate, -gallate, -phthalate and -terephthalate ions in aqueous solutions. Our purpose was to determine whether there is an association taking place or not in these systems, and to determine quantitatively the association constants and other thermodynamic parameters. In this paper we start with the sodium salts as an example of the monovalent salts to enable comparing such organic salts with those of inorganic ones. The values obtained here will be used in any corrections to be needed for the study of the Ca and Mg salts of these same organic ligands

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